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Modeling Liquid-Mediated Interactions for Close-to-Substrate Magnetic Microparticle Transport in Dynamic Magnetic Field Landscapes

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the on-chip motion of magnetic particles in a microfluidic environment is key to realizing magnetic particle-based Lab-on-a-chip systems for medical diagnostics. In this work, a simulation model is established to quantify the trajectory of a single particle moving close to a polymer surface in a quiescent liquid. The simulations include hydrodynamic, magnetostatic, and Derjaguin–Landau–Verwey–Overbeek (DLVO) interactions. They are applied to particle motion driven by a dynamically changing magnetic field landscape created by engineered parallel-stripe magnetic domains superposed by a homogeneous, time-varying external magnetic field. The simulation model is adapted to experiments in terms of fluid-particle interactions with the magnetic field landscape approximated by analytic equations under the assumption of surface charges. Varying simulation parameters, we especially clarify the impact of liquid-mediated DLVO interactions, which are essential for diagnostic applications, on the 3D trajectory of the particle. A comparison to experimental results validates our simulation approach.

1 | Introduction

The actuation of magnetic particles in a microfluidic environment via magnetic fields has high application potential in biosensing Lab-on-a-chip systems [1, 2]. Due to their large surface-to-volume ratio and flexibility in chemical surface properties, magnetic particles are already playing a significant role in lab-based bio-detection assays [2]. They are commercially available and come in different sizes, surface functionalizations, and magnetic properties [2]. When implemented in Lab-on-a-chip devices, magnetic particles move close to an underlying substrate surface, immersed in a fluid. An established scheme for achieving fast and robust on-chip particle actuation is magnetophoresis by dynamically superposing magnetic stray field landscapes above

micromagnetic structures with varying external homogeneous magnetic fields [3, 4] (sometimes also termed traveling wave magnetophoresis [5]). These structures may either be arrays of specifically shaped magnets [6–8], magnetic domains forming naturally [9], or imprinted artificially in topographically flat magnetic thin films [10]. Although previous works introduced clever designs for micromagnetic patterns and emerging magnetic stray field landscapes in order to realize target Lab-on-a-chip functionalities [8, 11–15], simulations for the analysis of particle trajectories rarely consider more than just the magnetic force acting on the particles.

In a recent attempt, the motion of a particle in the third dimension has been included in trajectory simulations, predicting

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FIGURE 1 | Model of the bilayer system with an analytic stray field box. Only the ferromagnetic $\text{Co}_{70}\text{Fe}_{30}$ layer is visible. The external field is applied in z - and x -direction according to Figure 3. The setup consists of multiple stripes in x -direction with periodically repeated head-to-head/tail-to-tail magnetization configuration, created by ion bombardment induced magnetic patterning. Typical stray field lines are given in arbitrary values from positive (red) to negative (blue) z -field component.

in addition to the lateral motion, also vertical upward jumps of the particles [16], which have been experimentally quantified for a specific magnetic stray field landscape using a defocusing-based 3D particle tracking method [17]. As it turns out, particles are jumping from one force equilibrium position (e.g., close to a domain wall) to another directly after inverting the direction of the external field. The upward movement is due to an inverted magnetic force repelling the particle from the substrate surface. Once the particle is approaching the adjacent force equilibrium position as a result of its lateral motion, the magnetic force turns attractive again, pulling the particle towards the substrate surface and concluding the jump. Little attention has been paid to the contribution of the liquid-mediated particle-substrate interaction, as the influence of the underlying substrate has been accounted for by only including an empirical z -dependent drag coefficient, leading to increased drag when the particle is closer to the substrate surface [16, 18]. However, if two solids surrounded by a fluid are close to each other, DLVO surface forces must be taken into account. DLVO interactions depend on the surface potentials of the particle and the substrate and on the ionic strength of the surrounding liquid. They are, therefore, important for biosensing devices where induced binding of an analyte, e.g., a protein, changes surface potentials and, by extension, the DLVO interaction. This has direct consequences for the 3D magnetic particle motion in a dynamic magnetic stray field landscape; measuring respective changes for the particles' 3D-trajectories may, therefore, indicate analyte binding events.

We seek in this work a thorough understanding of the multiparameter space that impacts the close-to-substrate 3D trajectory of a single micron-sized particle in a dynamically transformed stray field landscape, stemming from a head-to-head/tail-to-tail magnetized parallel-stripe domain pattern of a topographically flat magnetic layer system (Figure 1). This understanding is achieved by introducing a simulation model that goes beyond the typical approach of calculating the acting magnetic force and the empirical height-dependent drag coefficient by integrating surface-dependent DLVO forces and a hydrodynamic coupling with the surrounding static fluid. In the specific example considered here, the particle is moving from a head-to-head domain wall to a tail-to-tail domain wall location upon quickly reversing the external magnetic field component perpendicular to the

substrate surface (z -direction) while applying a constant field in the parallel-to-surface ($+x$)-direction (Figure 1).

Previously, the motion of spherical particles in viscous fluids has been approximated by a Stokes drag for laminar flow [19]. Alternatively, complex hydrodynamics and magnetic particle interactions have been solved by finite element simulations using Navier–Stokes and continuous Maxwell equations [20], yet still, the interaction of particles with the fluid has also been approximated by the Stokes drag. The development of numerical methods to describe magnetic particles in fluids is strongly influenced by the research of magnetorheological fluids, either by continuous or discrete approaches [21]. Here, we are interested in describing magnetic particle motion, accounting for full hydrodynamic interactions close to a flat surface.

In a previous work, we computed magnetically saturated particles in discretized lattice Boltzmann fluid dynamics [22], which is implemented in the soft-matter simulation environment ESPResSo [23]. In the present work, in contrast, the particle is superparamagnetic and not fully saturated. The working point lies, in our case, on the ascending slope of the particle's magnetization curve. Mass, volume, magnetic susceptibility, and magnetization act directly in the center of the particle, which moves in the effective field resulting from the vector sum of the magnetic stray field landscape and the external field. DLVO forces act at the particle's surface, depending on adhesion and electrical charge properties of both particle and substrate surfaces. Gravitation and buoyancy forces act in the center of the particle as well. In the simulation, the particle interacts indirectly with the surrounding fluid, where fictive fluid molecules perform consecutive propagation and collision processes. The movement of the particle acts on the fictive fluid molecules and vice versa for a full two-way hydrodynamic interaction.

Our proposed simulation model includes a large number of parameters, some of which are very sensitive to small changes. However, not all parameters can be experimentally quantified to the precision required for tuning the computational model. In this work, we probe the sensitivity of a particle's 3D trajectory to changes in these simulation parameters, allowing for a better understanding and control of particle trajectories in experiments and Lab-on-a-chip devices. The validity of our model is confirmed by comparing simulated trajectories with experimental results obtained by using standard parameters.

2 | Methods

2.1 | Experimental Setup

For tracking the 3D motion of magnetic particles, an optical defocusing-based approach [17] has been used. Briefly, the setup consists of an optical reflected-light microscope using a $100\times$ Nikon objective (leading to a small depth of focus), equipped with a movable sample stage surrounded by a coil arrangement providing the homogeneous magnetic field pulses in any direction and a high-speed video camera (Optronics CR450 \times 2). The video camera has been operated with 1000 frames per second at $800\text{ px} \times 600\text{ px}$ image resolution. Pulses in x - and z -directions (see Figure 1 for the used coordinate system) for inducing particle

motion are trapezoidal with plateaus at 1 mT in x - and at ± 8 mT in z -direction. For the motion step investigated in this work, the z -field switches from +8 to -8 mT within 20 ms at constant x -field.

2.2 | Microfluidic Chip

The substrate of the microfluidic chip consists of an exchange bias thin film layer system starting with 10 nm Cu as a buffer layer, followed by 30 nm Ir₁₇Mn₈₃ as the antiferromagnetic layer, 10 nm Co₇₀Fe₃₀ as the ferromagnetic layer and finished by 10 nm Au as a capping layer, deposited via rf-sputtering on a naturally-oxidized Si wafer (1.5 cm × 1.5 cm). After deposition, the sample was treated with a field cooling procedure to initialize the exchange bias direction, heating it up to 300°C inside an in-plane magnetic field of 145 mT for 60 min. The field-cooled sample was patterned into parallel-stripe domains via light-ion bombardment induced magnetic patterning [24, 25]. It was coated with a resist layer structured into periodically repeated 5µm stripes using optical lithography. The thickness of the resist was chosen so that 10keV He ions do not penetrate through it. After treatment with 10keV He ion bombardment with a dose of 10¹⁵ ions/cm² inside an in-plane magnetic field (100 mT) that is directed antiparallel to the initial exchange bias direction, the sample exhibits a periodic domain pattern with 5µm wide stripes and a head-to-head/tail-to-tail magnetization configuration (Figure 1). The resist structure is then removed from the sample surface. A polymer layer, Poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA), with a thickness of 150 nm was deposited on the sample surface via spin coating to serve as a spacer layer and prevent sticking of the particles to the metallic sample surface. A Parafilm with a window of 8 mm × 8mm has then been adhered to the substrate, into which the solution with the magnetic particles has been pipetted. The container was then sealed with a glass cover slip.

2.3 | DLVO Forces

DLVO forces account for the electrodynamic van-der-Waals interaction between two surfaces separated by a fluid and the electrostatic Coulomb interaction inherent to the surface adsorption of ions from the fluidic environment [18]. The DLVO theory can be employed to characterize the van-der-Waals force F_{vdW} and the electrostatic force F_{el} acting between particle and substrate surfaces in the investigated system. The interaction energy between two bodies of arbitrary geometry is given by the interatomic van-der-Waals potential $w(r) = -C/r^6$ [26].

In addition, the Hamaker constant $A_{132} = \pi^2 C \rho_1 \rho_2$ can be used to specify the interaction of the bodies [26]. C describes an interaction parameter, while ρ_1 and ρ_2 are the number of atoms in each body, respectively. For a spherical particle of material 1 with radius r , which is positioned within a medium 3 at a distance z from material 2 with an infinitely flat surface, the van-der-Waals force can be expressed as the following, using an appropriate Hamaker constant A_{132} [18, 27]:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{vdW}}(z) = -\frac{A_{132}r}{6z^2} \left(\frac{1}{1 + 14z/\lambda_{\text{ret}}} \right) \mathbf{e}_z \quad (1)$$

λ_{ret} represents a characteristic retardation wavelength for the interaction and \mathbf{e}_z stands for the unit vector in z -direction.

The electrostatic interaction force $F_{\text{el}}(z)$ between two surfaces immersed in a fluid is the consequence of the formation of an electrical double layer at each surface caused by the accumulation of positively and negatively charged ions from the fluid [28]. This double layer impacts the surface potentials Ψ_p and Ψ_s of a spherical particle and a flat surface, respectively. Attractive or repulsive electrostatic forces $F_{\text{el}}(z)$ between particle and substrate surfaces can be calculated by considering the respective surface potentials [18]:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{el}}(z) = \frac{2\pi\epsilon\kappa r}{1 - e^{-2\kappa z}} \left[2\Psi_s\Psi_p e^{-\kappa z} \mp (\Psi_s^2 + \Psi_p^2) e^{-2\kappa z} \right] \mathbf{e}_z \quad (2)$$

with ϵ being the permittivity of the surrounding fluid medium. The Debye-Hückel inverse double layer thickness κ is a function of the temperature T and the ionic strength of the fluid I [18]. It can be expressed by [18]

$$\kappa = \sqrt{\frac{2000N_A e^2 \cdot I}{\epsilon k_B T}} \quad (3)$$

where N_A is the Avogadro constant, e the elementary charge, and k_B the Boltzmann's constant. The \mp sign in Equation (2) represents two different model assumptions. The negative sign assumes constant surface potentials for the interacting surfaces, while the positive sign refers to constant charge densities [18]. The former is more applicable if surface charging processes occur on a much faster timescale than the interaction of the surfaces, and the latter is typically more useful when the situation is reversed. The two limiting cases for the model concur with separation distances larger than the double layer thickness [18], which should be true for the considered system. In Section 3.2, we show the difference and the significance for our simulation model. From an experimental view, surface potentials are not easily accessible. Therefore, Ψ_p and Ψ_s are typically approximated by the respective zeta potentials ζ_p and ζ_s [29]. The zeta potential describes the electric potential present at the shearing plane between mobile and immobile ions surrounding a fluid-immersed surface [28]. It can be experimentally quantified by light scattering of electrophoretically moved particles together with a fitting electrokinetic treatment [30]. Please note that electrostatic forces depend on the pH level of the fluid.

2.4 | Magnetic Particles

Superparamagnetic Dynabead M-270 Carboxylic Acid particles from Thermo Fisher with a diameter of 2.8 µm in distilled water have been used. An effective magnetic field \mathbf{H}_{eff} induces a magnetic moment \mathbf{m} inside the particle proportional to its volume V and effective susceptibility $\chi_{\text{eff}} = 3\chi/(3 + \chi)$, which is calculated from the magnetic susceptibility χ with the demagnetization factor of a sphere $N_k = 1/3$.

$$\mathbf{m} = V\chi_{\text{eff}}\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}} \quad (4)$$

\mathbf{H}_{eff} results from the magnetic stray field landscape and the alternating applied external field \mathbf{H}_{ext} . Magnetic field contributions of neighboring particles will be neglected in this work. With small applied fields, the magnetic susceptibility can be assumed to be constant, but with increasing field, the particle's magnetic moment saturates. The resulting magnetization curve can also be approximated by the Langevin function, which is explained in Section S3, where both the dimensionless parameter a and the saturation magnetic moment m_s need to be tuned to fit the experimental measurements, given for Dynabeads M-270 in [31]. The working point of the magnetic particle trajectories analyzed within this manuscript is on the ascending slope of the magnetization curve. For comparison, we show the results of magnetic particle trajectories in the saturated magnetization regime in Section S4.

The magnetic gradient force \mathbf{F}_m on the particle is computed by the negative gradient of its potential energy in the field $\mu_0\mu_r\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}$ with the permeability of free space μ_0 and the permeability of the surrounding fluid $\mu_r \approx 1$.

$$\mathbf{F}_m = \mu_0 \nabla(\mathbf{m}\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}) \quad (5)$$

Please keep in mind that we compute \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{F}_m in the center of the superparamagnetic particle, assuming a homogeneous field and magnetization inside the particle. Dynabeads M-270 consist of iron oxide nanoparticles trapped inside the micron-sized particle by a polymer shell. The iron oxide nanoparticles can form small clusters [32], which may lead to an inhomogeneous magnetization inside the particle. In Section S3, we average multiple points on the surface of a magnetic particle to examine the influence of an inhomogeneous field on \mathbf{F}_m .

2.5 | Lattice Boltzmann Fluid Dynamics

The lattice Boltzmann method is based on a discretized lattice grid with a uniform grid length. Fictive fluid molecules on the grid points perform consecutive propagation and collision. Macroscopic fluid properties can be obtained by distribution functions f_k of these fictive molecules in space x and time t .

$$\underbrace{f_k(x + e_k\delta_t, t + \delta_t)}_{\text{streaming}} = \underbrace{f_k(x, t) - \frac{(f_k(x, t) - f_k^{\text{eq}}(x, t))}{\tau}}_{\text{collision}} + \underbrace{F_k(x, t)}_{\text{external forces}} \quad (6)$$

ESPResSo uses 3 dimensions with 19 discrete velocities, $k = 0 \dots 18$, the D3Q19 version of the lattice Boltzmann method [33]. e_k is the discrete velocity vector, δ_t is the time step, τ denotes the relaxation time, f_k^{eq} is the equilibrium function depending on macroscopic variables velocity $v(t)$ and density $\rho(t)$.

Magnetic particles are 2-way coupled with the lattice Boltzmann fluid lattice. Given the Newton's equation of motion, the force on a particle with mass m , position x and time t can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{F}(x, t) = m \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = \mathbf{F}_{\text{DLVO}} + \mathbf{F}_m + \mathbf{F}_d \quad (7)$$

with DLVO forces \mathbf{F}_{DLVO} , magnetic gradient force \mathbf{F}_m and fluidic drag force \mathbf{F}_d . Equations (6) and (7) represent the motion of the

fluid and the motion of the particle, respectively. They act on different meshes, the fixed Eulerian grid points of the fluid and the moving Lagrangian center of the particle. Coupling of the two schemes is done by a method of Ahrlichs and Dünweg [34], applying a drag force

$$\mathbf{F}_d = -\gamma(\mathbf{v}_p - \mathbf{v}_f) \quad (8)$$

\mathbf{F}_d is inversely proportional to the velocity difference of the particle velocity \mathbf{v}_p and the fluid velocity \mathbf{v}_f at the specific particle position multiplied by the drag coefficient γ , which is given in Ns m^{-1} units [35]. \mathbf{v}_f is hereby interpolated from nearby fixed grid points. To conserve the total momentum of fluid and particle the opposite force $-\mathbf{F}_d$ is distributed back to the nearby grid points and acts as an additional external force term in Equation (6). The distribution is inversely proportional to the cuboidal volumes with opposite corners being the particle's center and the grid point [34].

Due to the discretization of the fluid lattice and the representation of the magnetic particle by mass points, γ needs to be calibrated, which is described in Section S2. Please note, that the discretization of the fluid lattice needs to be chosen such that the particle diameter is smaller than the lattice grid length, which means a single particle should fit multiple times into a single fluid lattice cell [22]. A finer resolution of the fluid lattice requires representation of a magnetic particle by a rigid arrangement of multiple mass points.

ESPResSo does not use predefined units. These can be set according to the underlying simulated phenomenon. In this work we set the time scale to $0.1 \mu\text{s}$, length scale to $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ and mass scale to 10^{-15} kg . Other physical quantities are either not scaled or a proper combination of time, length, and mass units.

The fluid parameters in this work are set for water at 20°C with density $\rho_F = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$, dynamic viscosity $\mu = 0.001 \text{ kgm}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, and relative permittivity $\epsilon_r = 80.1$.

The boundaries of the simulation box are set with the no-slip boundary condition, which results in zero fluid velocity right at the substrate surface. We emphasize that using a simple fluidic force term, rather than the 2-way hydrodynamic interaction of particles and lattice Boltzmann fluid, causes a slight deviation of the particle trajectories, due to the missing feedback from the fluid molecules.

2.6 | Magnetic Stray Field Landscape

In this work, we use an analytic solution to obtain the magnetic stray field landscape generated by a parallel-stripe domain pattern with remanent in-plane magnetizations forming head-to-head and tail-to-tail domain walls with flat interfaces.

In micromagnetic simulations, we are limited in simulation size [36]. The dimension of finite elements to resolve nucleation and domain wall movement is typically a few nanometers only. To consider the size of the original bilayer system, we are using an analytic solution of the magnetic field created by cuboidal permanent magnets [37].

The magnetization inside these magnets is assumed to be homogeneous and parallel to one of the cuboid's axes, in our case the x -axis (compare Figure 1). Since the magnetic polarization \mathbf{J} is perpendicular to the interfaces between the stripes, these faces have a surface charge density $\sigma = |\mathbf{J}|$. The magnetic field by uniformly charged rectangular surfaces can be calculated analytically at each point in space, which is shown in [37]. Superposing all charged surface fields, the full stray field landscape is obtained.

With this, it is possible to treat particle motion in a magnetic stray field landscape created by the domain configuration of Figure 1 with a depth along the y -coordinate of $50 \mu\text{m}$. Note that two touching domains with opposite magnetic orientation form a domain wall. By changing the magnetic configuration, e.g., applying varying external magnetic fields, this domain wall can move. Domain wall formation is not considered when treating the magnetic stray field landscape by analytic equations. Therefore, we talk about interfaces between adjacent stripe domains in the simulations. These interfaces are treated as infinitely thin.

Here, we simulate a single jump from a head-to-head to a tail-to-tail interface above the bilayer system. The magnetic field landscape considers the superposition of the related interfaces and all other interfaces in the system. The inclusion of domain wall formation would reduce the magnitude of the resulting stray field above an interface. In this work, this reduction is accounted for by an additional thickness of the polymer spacer layer.

Note, that additional minor force contributions acting on the magnetic particles are summarized in Section S1.

3 | Experimental and Simulated Particle Trajectories

In this section, we demonstrate the effect of varying the model parameters on a particle's equilibrium height above the polymer surface when resting, and the jump height as well as jump duration, initialized by switching the z -component of the external magnetic field.

3.1 | Experimentally Determined Particle Jump

The motion of water-dispersed superparamagnetic particles on top of the magnetically patterned substrate was induced by magnetic field pulses in z - and x -directions of $\mu_0 H_{z,\text{max}} = 8 \text{ mT}$ and $\mu_0 H_{x,\text{max}} = 1 \text{ mT}$, respectively. Each field pulse in the z -direction forced a particle jump between positions of neighboring domain walls (denoted as interfaces in the simulation), e.g., from a head-to-head wall to a tail-to-tail wall. With a positive x -component of the field, a forward jump in the $+x$ -direction can be chosen. We determined the jump trajectory for such a motion event by applying an optical defocusing-based 3D particle tracking method, in analogy to the results presented in [17].

The z -coordinates of five individual particles measured for different locations on the substrate are shown in Figure 2 as a

FIGURE 2 | Vertical trajectories of Dynabead M-270 superparamagnetic particles moving on top of a polymer-covered, magnetic stripe domain patterned substrate after applying time-varying external magnetic fields. The evolution of the vertical z -position as a function of lateral x -position was determined by optical defocusing-based 3D particle tracking. Measured data points (squares) and a 4th-degree polynomial fit (solid lines) are compared to a simulation with standard parameters (thick dashed line) shown in Table 1. The average of all polynomial fits is given as a dotted line, with the shaded area representing the experimental uncertainty. The z -position was determined for the center of the particles and normalized to zero. The x -position is given from one interface (domain wall) to the next one within the magnetically patterned substrate. Negative z -positions at the end of the jump are measurement artifacts and are not caused by particles physically entering the polymer layer.

function of the lateral x -position. The jump height and duration were determined for each particle and subsequently averaged to obtain about $1.4 \mu\text{m}$ as the average jump height and about 7 ms as the average jump duration. Differences in individual particle trajectories arise from variations in the magnetic properties of the particles (these particles typically exhibit a distribution in size and magnetic content) and variations in the magnetic stray field landscape caused by different domain wall properties, which is inherent to the fabrication procedure. By averaging over different particles and domain wall positions, we try to account for these variations. The final z -positions after the jump show a slight deviation as compared to the start z -positions before the jump, i.e., the particles end up at lower z -positions compared to when they started. The defocusing-based 3D tracking method is sensitive to the lighting conditions in the experiment; thus, we mainly explain this deviation with inhomogeneous sample illumination. It has no significant impact on the determination of jump duration; for the jump height, it is accounted for by the experimental uncertainty, shown as the shaded area in Figure 2 for the averaged experimental data.

For comparison, we show the result of a simulation with standard model parameters (dashed line), which we will introduce and discuss in the next section. Note that due to the experimental measurement uncertainty, we cannot resolve changes in particle z -position that are lower than 500 nm. Particle jumps with a height below this uncertainty are, therefore, solely measured as a lateral movement in the x -direction.

TABLE 1 | Initial parameter set of the simulation model. Parameters marked with * can be tuned in the experiment.

Parameter	Value	Unit	Comment
ESPResSo unit conversion			
length	l	10^{-7}	$\hat{=} 0.1 \mu\text{m}$
time	t	10^{-7}	$\hat{=} 0.1 \mu\text{s}$
weight	w	10^{-15}	$\hat{=} 10^{-15} \text{kg}$
Fluid			
channel	$50 \times 50 \times 100$	μm^3	
grid length	100		$\hat{=} 10 \mu\text{m}$ lattice grid length
drag coefficient	γ	Ns m^{-1}	see Section S2
*density	ρ_F	kg m^{-3}	water 20°C
*dynamic viscosity	μ	$\text{kg m}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$	water 20°C
*relative permittivity	ϵ_r	80.1	water 20°C
Dynabeads M-270			
diameter	d	2.8	μm
density	ρ_P	1600	kg m^{-3}
saturation magnetization [38]	M_S	10.24	kA m^{-1}
magnetic susceptibility [38]	χ	0.479	
Magnetic field			
*external magnetic field z	$\mu_0 H_{\text{ext},z}$	± 8	mT
*external magnetic field x	$\mu_0 H_{\text{ext},x}$	1	mT
*switching time	t_s	20	ms
DLVO			
Hamaker constant [17]	A_{132}	1.23e-20	J
*Debye length [28]	$1/\kappa$	100	nm
*Particle zeta potential [39]	ζ_P	-28.28	mV
*Substrate zeta potential [17]	ζ_S	-65	mV
*polymer thickness	t_{PMMA}	2	μm
			spacer layer between magnetic bilayer and fluid channel, artificially increased due to overestimated analytic stray field
			depends on fluid, particle and substrate properties
			depends on pH level
			depends on pH level
			depends on pH level
			time to change sign for $\mu_0 H_{\text{ext},z}$
			+8 mT to -8 mT in 100 steps
			see Sections S3 and S4
			see Section S3
			other particles may lead to different trajectories, see Section S4

FIGURE 3 | Simulation result with standard parameter set. (a) A magnetic particle's trajectory (z - and x -position) together with the applied external magnetic fields ($H_{\text{ext},z}$ and $H_{\text{ext},x}$), and (b) force contributions are shown for the duration of a single particle jump. A blue dashed circle at equilibrium z -position in (a) depicts the particle size and demonstrates the gap between the particle surface and the polymer surface. Interface positions of touching stripes (horizontal red dashed lines) are important for the particle's lateral x -position. Vertical dashed lines show the different temporal force regimes from equilibrium position, repelling from the polymer surface, attracting to the polymer surface to the next equilibrium position. The Van-der-Waals force F_{vdw} and the force from gravity and buoyancy F_{gb} are negligible and not shown. Note that F_{el} is used with the negative sign of Equation (2).

3.2 | Simulation of a Particle Jump

We define a set of initial parameters in Table 1 as a starting point for our theoretical study. The computed particle trajectory is compared to the experimental result. By varying the simulation parameters, we examine their impact and assess the model's sensitivity to these changes.

In Figure 3a, we show the temporal evolution of a jump simulation for the parameters of Table 1. They have been chosen according to experimental measurements (compare Sections 2.1 and 3.1), literature investigation, calibration of the simulation model, and by selecting an accurate working point of the magnetic particle (compare Sections s2, s3 and s4). All parameters in Table 1 marked with a * can be tuned in the experiment, but are not necessarily easy to determine.

We start with an initial particle position right above a head-to-head interface at a distance of $2\ \mu\text{m}$ to the polymer layer and a positive external magnetic field $\mu_0 H_{\text{ext},z} = 8\ \text{mT}$ and $\mu_0 H_{\text{ext},x} = 1\ \text{mT}$. First, the particle relaxes to find its equilibrium position and then we apply a single field pulse reversing $H_{\text{ext},z}$ from $+8$ to $-8\ \text{mT}$ within $20\ \text{ms}$ at constant $H_{\text{ext},x}$. Note that the particle position is given for the center of the particle. The magnetization of the particle is pointing in the direction of the external magnetic field (compare Section S3).

With positive field values and a positive magnetization, the particle is attracted to a head-to-head interface. After only a few milliseconds, the particle finds an equilibrium x - and z -position, which is slightly shifted to the positive x -direction away from the head-to-head interface and with a certain distance z above the polymer surface. With the parameters of Table 1, the equilibrium distance between particle surface and polymer surface is about $280\ \text{nm}$ (compare blue dashed lines for particle and polymer surface in Figure 3a). The equilibrium height is defined by balancing the magnetic force F_m and the electrostatic force F_{el} (Figure 3b, compare also Figure S4). We are using F_{el} with the negative sign of Equation (2). Using the positive sign results in a slightly different equilibrium height only. The rest of the particle trajectory is about the same. All other force contributions, the van-der-Waals force F_{vdw} and the force from gravity and buoyancy F_{gb} [40], are negligibly small. A comparison of all force contributions with a given distance between polymer and particle surface is shown and discussed in Section S5.1.

The particle starts to move from head-to-head to the next tail-to-tail interface, whereby the jump direction is controlled by $H_{\text{ext},x}$. The particle height is slowly increasing with a force balance of F_{el} and F_m (Figure 3b). This initial increase in particle height cannot be seen in the experiments due to the measurement uncertainty. When the external field $H_{\text{ext},z}$ is pointing in the negative direction, the particle magnetization is reversed as well, and the particle is repelled by the head-to-head interface. F_m gets dominant (Figure 3b) and the particle height is increasing faster. The particle reaches a maximum height of about $1.3\ \mu\text{m}$ above the equilibrium height. The maximum height is reached between the head-to-head and tail-to-tail interfaces when the repulsion of the head-to-head interface is overcome by the attraction of the tail-to-tail interface. F_{el} becomes more influential, and the equilibrium position is found close to the tail-to-tail interface. Please note that we do not show the fluid force contribution F_d , as it is handled with the 2-way coupling of the lattice Boltzmann method described in Section 2.5.

In the Supporting Information, we show a video of a full simulation run with the standard parameters shown in Table 1.

3.3 | Variation of Model Parameters

In the previous sections, we have shown that the simulation model for predicting magnetic particle trajectories describes the experiments qualitatively well. It contains, however, a larger number of parameters, rendering a quantitative comparison challenging. We, therefore, investigate the sensitivity of the simulated jump height, duration, and particle equilibrium height before and after the jump on these parameters. Figure 4 shows the variation

FIGURE 4 | Effect of parameter variation on the characteristic quantities jump duration, jump height, and equilibrium height for a simulated particle jump. The bold numbers and the color code represent the respective quantity. The gray numbers below the simulation results give the low, standard, and high values of the specific parameter on the left. Here, t_{PMNA} is the polymer layer thickness varied between 1.5 and 2.5 μm , χ is the particle's magnetic susceptibility, varied between 0.3 and 0.7, z - and x - components of the external field have been varied between 7 and 9 mT (z -component) and 0.8 and 1.2 mT (x -component), the switching time t_s for the external field has been varied between 10 and 30 ms, the Debye length $1/\kappa$ for the electrostatic interaction has been varied between 80 and 120 nm, and the zeta potentials for particle ζ_p and substrate ζ_s surfaces have been varied between -40 and -20 mV (particle) and -75 and -55 mV (substrate). A trendline of the results is compared to the experimental values shown as a dashed line. Note that the equilibrium height cannot be experimentally measured.

of the individual parameters, keeping all other parameters at their standard values (Table 1). The simulation results for jump duration and height are compared to the experiments, which is not possible for the equilibrium height, as we could not experimentally quantify this property so far. When determining the jump duration from the simulated trajectories, we account for the experimental z -position measurement uncertainty of 500 nm to perform a sensible comparison. Hence, we count the start of the simulated particle jump as soon as its z -position increases by more than 500 nm after reversing $H_{\text{ext},z}$.

3.3.1 | Polymer Layer Thickness t_{PMMA}

An increase of the gap between the ferromagnetic layer of the underlying thin film system and the particle, realized by an increase of the polymer thickness from 1.5 to 2.5 μm , reduces the magnetic stray field while maintaining the repulsive electrostatic particle surface-polymer surface interaction. This pushes the particle to a higher equilibrium position and induces a higher and longer jump.

3.3.2 | Magnetic Susceptibility χ

A reduction in the magnetic susceptibility of the particle from 0.7 to 0.3 drastically increases the resulting characteristics. The particle's magnetic moment is reduced, leading to a decreased magnetic force at maintained electrostatic repulsion from the polymer surface and, therefore, a higher equilibrium position, a larger jump height, and a remarkably increased jump duration.

3.3.3 | External Fields $H_{\text{ext},z}$ and $H_{\text{ext},x}$

The z -component of the external field has negligible effects in the range between 9 and 7 mT, while the x -component seems to be of major importance. Only a small variation of $H_{\text{ext},x}$ yielded significant changes for the jump duration and height. $H_{\text{ext},x}$ is necessary to control the path of the particle and causes a slight shift of the equilibrium x -position away from the interface center. With $H_{\text{ext},x} = 0.8$ mT, the equilibrium x -position is closer to the interface, which results in a higher z -component and a smaller x -component of the magnetic gradient field during the main jump. Consequently, the jump is higher but lasts longer. With $H_{\text{ext},x} = 1.2$ mT the effect is reversed.

3.3.4 | Switching Time t_s

The jump height depends sensitively on the switching time of the external z -field between the two plateaus $H_{z,\text{max}}$ and $-H_{z,\text{max}}$. With a faster switch (10 ms switching time), the jump is much higher with a longer jump duration, whereas increasing the switching time up to 30 ms lowers the height and slightly reduces the jump duration. The equilibrium position is about the same for the different switching times.

3.3.5 | Debye Length $1/\kappa$ and Zeta Potentials ζ

Increasing the Debye length from 80 to 120 nm increases all characteristic quantities likely due to a stronger electrostatic repulsion from the polymer surface, weakening the influence

of the magnetic force. Lowering the magnitude of the zeta potential for the particle surface ζ_p from -40 to -20 mV results in a small change of the equilibrium position due to the varied electrostatic force from 324 to 234 nm, respectively. The same trend is observable for changing the zeta potential of the substrate surface ζ_s between -75 and -55 , whereas the changes in the equilibrium position are less significant in this case. The simulations yielded no significant changes in the jump height and duration when modifying the zeta potentials of the particle or the substrate surface.

3.3.6 | Other Parameters

In the following, we discuss the influence of other parameters that are not shown in Figure 4. A variation of the particle's saturation magnetization M_s is negligible because the working point of the magnetic particle is in the increasing slope of the magnetization curve (compare Figure S2 and Section S4).

Changing the sign in Equation (2) from negative to positive does not decisively alter the particle trajectory, but only slightly increases the equilibrium height by a few nm.

Results for a changing van-der-Waals force F_{vdw} are not shown, as it is orders of magnitude smaller than the other forces, but might have a major effect at very small equilibrium heights.

Gravitational and buoyancy effects are neglected as well, for similar reasons.

Fluid properties and the calibration of the drag coefficient are discussed in Section S2. Changing one of the fluid parameters requires recalibration of the drag coefficient γ , which is not shown. A slight increase of γ minorly raises the particle trajectory and vice versa. Particle properties, like diameter and density, are kept constant as well to keep the drag calibration comprehensible.

4 | Discussion and Conclusion

A simulation of magnetic particle motion, immersed in a fluid and close to a polymer surface, activated by a dynamically transformed magnetic stray field landscape, follows multiple physical principles. These are fluid dynamics and the interaction with a rigid particle, gradient fields of the magnetic stray field and superposed external field contributions, surface charges repelling and attracting the particle according to electrostatic and van-der-Waals forces, and other minor contributions, like gravitation and Brownian motion. Each of the included physical principles is modeled by using a set of parameters. Understanding the effect of each parameter on the resulting trajectories of a particle allows us to control the movement and, further on, may offer the possibility to sense analytes (e.g., proteins) bound to the particles, which is crucial for medical applications.

Here, we are focusing on parallel micron-sized stripe domains with a periodically alternating head-to-head/tail-to-tail magnetization configuration, which generates the necessary magnetic stray field landscape for the magnetic particle actuation. The magnetic stray field in the simulations is obtained from analytical

equations of cuboidal permanent magnets. For small distances, where the domain walls have a considerable impact, large-scale micromagnetic simulations are required, which are currently not yet possible due to size limitations in the computation.

In this work, we implemented all force contributions into the lattice Boltzmann framework of ESPResSo, which allows the dynamic interaction of the particle with the surrounding fluid. Repelling electrostatic and attracting magnetic forces lead the particle to a certain equilibrium position, whose absolute values cannot yet be measured in experiments. By applying a reversing external magnetic field, slightly bent with an additional field term, the particle can jump from a position above one shared interface of neighboring stripe domains (domain wall) to the next.

A single particle jump starts with a slow increase in height right after the external magnetic field begins to switch. This is caused by a reduced magnetic gradient force with respect to the repelling electrostatic force. After the field crosses zero, the particle magnetization is reversed, and the initial attraction to a head-to-head or tail-to-tail interface is now repelling the particle, which causes the actual jump. This jump could be visualized in 3D measurements, yet the slight increase in height right after the field started to switch was not observed due to the measurement uncertainty, leading to a certain threshold, after which a particle movement in the vertical z -direction can be detected. This threshold is important to be included in the definition of a jump duration; otherwise, simulation and experiments cannot be compared.

Variations of the model parameters have shown that the magnetic properties can change the particle trajectories to a large extent, whereas electrostatic forces primarily influence the equilibrium position of a particle above the polymer spacer layer and its trajectory only slightly. This changes when particles are moving closer to the polymer surface. Here, temporary sticking or even permanent adhesion can be caused by, for instance, van-der-Waals interactions. In current experiments, the particle equilibrium position is challenging to quantify; the simulation results provide, therefore, valuable predictions. In Section S5, we provide additional information on height-dependent force contributions, initial adherence of particles and its effect on particle trajectories, as well as the transition of particles from an initial position to the equilibrium position.

The most influential parameters found in this work are related to the magnetic gradient force: the polymer layer thickness, which changes the magnetic stray field magnitude; the magnetic susceptibility of the particles; and the applied magnetic field parallel to the polymer surface and perpendicular to the stripe domains' long axis (compare Figure 1). The switching time for the external field also has a significant influence on the particle trajectories according to our simulations.

The magnetic field applied parallel to the bilayer is necessary to control the direction of the particle jump. Slightly changing this field shifts the x -equilibrium position, thus changing the magnetic gradient force, which alters the particle trajectory. An increase in the field brings the equilibrium position closer to the interface of touching stripes, with the effect of a higher jump that lasts longer. By reducing the field, the effect is reversed.

The magnetic properties of the used superparamagnetic particles reported in literature are ambiguous; an absolute comparison of the simulation results with the experiment should be treated with caution. An inhomogeneous distribution of magnetic material within the overall superparamagnetic micron-sized particle may be a reason for that. For future investigations, the developed model could be used to characterize the unknown magnetic properties of single particles by comparing their experimentally observed motion with accurately predicted trajectories.

Additionally, the applied magnetic fields from the Helmholtz coils need to be set carefully. Microscope heads and other equipment positioned close to the sample and, therefore, potentially influencing the magnetic fields, should be used with special care.

Furthermore, physical rotations of the particle after magnetic field switching, caused by Brownian relaxation of its magnetic moment, could further impact the experimentally observed 3D trajectory. For the investigated particles, we could not observe such rotations; hence, we assume a reorientation of the particle's magnetic moment solely via Néel relaxation and neglect any physical rotational movements in our simulation model.

Even though we investigated many parameters in our magnetic particle trajectory simulations, some further uncertainties need to be thoroughly examined. A deviation of experimental results from the simulation predictions is still present. An appropriate analysis of the height-dependent drag coefficients of spherical particles moving close to a flat surface might be able to explain this issue [41–43]. In this work, we already considered a varying distance between the particle surface and the surface of the underlying substrate, however, the influence of this varied distance on the flow resistance originating from the surrounding fluid and acting on the particle is not reflected. A first attempt for implementing a height-dependent drag into the simulation is taken in the Section S5.4, but must be further explored in future work.

Changing the particle geometry will have major effects on the resulting trajectories as well. Increasing the time resolution of the 3D imaging experiment and also increasing the vertical spatial resolution may deliver important insights into the particle trajectories. Yet the theoretical insights gained in our study pave the way toward more advanced particle motion experiments, especially concerning analyte detection in medical Lab-on-a-chip systems. Our simulations reveal that the binding of an analyte to a particle, which comes with a change in its surface potential, may lead to a significant change in its equilibrium position above the chip surface. Detection with optical methods could present a simple yet efficient way to quantify this change in equilibrium position and, accordingly, the amount of bound analyte.

Author Contributions

M.G. and R.H. conceptualized the project, experiments and simulations. R.H. performed experiments and data analysis. M.G. carried out simulations. M.G. and R.H. wrote the manuscript. A.K. and H.O. analyzed simulation data and improved visualizations. M.G., R.H., A.E. and T.S. contributed to supervision and funding acquisition. All authors contributed to reviewing and editing the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the experimental measurements in Figure 2 have been included as part of the Supplementary materials. All other data generated or analyzed during this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File 1: ppsc70083-sup-0001-SuppMat.pdf.

Supporting File 2: ppsc70083-sup-0002-VideoS1.mp4.

Supporting File 3: ppsc70083-sup-0003-particle-experiments.zip.